

Coping With the New Experience

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this paper is to analyze what can happen to us from a philosophical point of view every time we are face with new situations and every time we have to make another choice that might not be placed into our comfort zone. Despite the fact each individual is different and we have our own personality and our own points of view and despite the fact that there are no two people who think the same one thing is sure: no one likes to be thrown into an unknown context. Throughout this journey called life even though we do not want it to happened we are oh fun faced with the unknown. How we deal with the new experiences that we are encountering will be what makes us or what breaks us. It is up to us to make the best with what we have or at least that's what we think or like to think. Maybe not all the questions will be answered with this paper but I hope that I can at least set of common ground and start exploring what lies beneath our choices.

KEYWORDS: experience, life, thoughts, individual, world

OUR MIND THROUGH OUR EXPERIENCE

“Ordinary physical objects are essentially publicly accessible (anyone can observe a chair) whereas minds are not (only I can directly observe my mind). Ordinary physical objects are also essentially extended in space – they have mass, shape, location and other spatial properties.”¹ the world that we know is made of both tangible and in Intangible things. For the most part we realize what we are being surrounded by. The tangible things are what we know as common existence because we can feel then we can touch that we can see them. We often rely on things that have a proper definition and a materialistic one the form or save zone in order for us to at least have a base to start from. As far as I'm concerned this is a great attribute to any human being. This particular aspect can give us the opportunity to at least have something to hold on to.

We tend to rely on things that we know are there when we come face to face with something that is different. Some may see this as being a big mistake because they might come with an argument that sounds like this:...well what would happen if we ever find ourselves into a place that is completely new to us, that has no common ground nor does it resemble any familiar place that might help us to find something to hold on to. Well you what happens in that moment?...we adapt. We try to put our vision and our thoughts into place, try to move forward and if we have nothing known to help us we create something else. We become what they call visionaries. Even if it's just for that small part. Even if it's just to survive in a known state of mind but an unknown environment.

“Thus the concept of environment is originally a social concept that tries to express the individual's dependence on society—i.e., it is related only to man. In a broad sense, however, this concept can be used to comprehend all the conditions on which a living creature depends.”² We are taught that because we are human beings we have the ability to make rational decisions based un true facts (or what we perceive as being true facts). But what happens when our minds are trying to make sense of it all and we are not thinking like we normally do. What happens when we reach a place in which the mind gets trapped in so many questions that we no lomnger have the same perception over life like we used to...even a few minutes ago? Some may wonder what are supposed to do in such moments. Others will start to ask themselves which is the right way to handle the situation...but how can you determine right from wrong when you don't know exactly what is right and what is wrong.

Others may try to work their way around the situation while others...I believe will start to question the life they live, or we live. Coping with a new experience is never easy. Maybe the asking part is not suitable for everyone and maybe some will wonder why we do it and what good does it bring but we cannot start to ask these tipes of questions and judge someone just because their way of handling something personal is not the same as our way. Some would say or claim that everything persists in its various

¹ Matt Carter, MINDS AND COMPUTERS. AN INTRODUCTION TO THE PHILOSOPHY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, Edinburgh University Press, Edinburgh, 2007, p.8

² Hans-Georg Gadamer, Truth and Method, Continuum, London, 2004, p.441

Coping With the New Experience

forms, regardless of the surroundings, regardless of the essence of time, of one's own self or of our own spirit. What makes us different or different at certain times or circumstances in our lives that is constantly endangered by energies, by space, universe, choices and decisions, perceptions and perspectives, identification and experiences is what makes us unique and at the end of the day this is what should matter the most.

Our own experiences define us through everything that the world and human existence has discovered, from the explanation of the self, of being and time, of the universe, of all sciences, which have met in an ambiguous paradox and define the things that transcend us, regardless of what has happened before or what will happen in the future we are all heading towards. It's like living above the world and not inside it. Experiences shape and change us. So is the paradox of time and perception. Nothing in this universe happens just once. The infinite goes in both directions. There are no unique events or singular moments. There is a mismatch, a discrepancy between what we know and what we do before we find our way.

„Obviously we can keep seeing things in a certain way while at the same time knowing that doing so is absurd in the world of understanding. And is it not language that operates in a creative way, reconciling these stratified living relationships.”³ The world as we know it is made of everything and nothing at the same time. But how can we be sure of that? Or how do we know where to start? Saying that not the language is the one who operates is completely true. Just think about it...just what is language without us behind it? At the end of the day it is just a tool that helps us express what we know so that others can be on the same page.

THE NEW WORLD

“Certainly one can inquire into the structure embracing all the worlds that man has ever experienced, which is simply the experience of the possibility of world, and in this sense we can indeed speak of an ontology of the world.”⁴ Starting with our first breath we open our own world and bring it into this known world. What we know as our safe bubble is in fact our own world. Something that will never leave us but at the same time something that we can leave. Opening up, getting out of that safe space, embracing this known world to others but unknown to us will eventually transform me, you or whoever identifies as a person into who we really are or into who we are meant to be.

“No one determinate entity—the soul, for example—lies within everything that lives as what is unchangeable behind a self altering appearance. It is the mystery of the nature of being itself, the one wise thing, the truly divine, that nevertheless manifests itself in the sudden shift between death and life.”⁵ We might just call our bubble our life – but what makes us or break us is how we look at it. And how we look at the unknown. Death as some may call it could be the end of everything. Everything that we know. But put things into perspective. Try and see both sides of the story. The end of this world is just the beginning of the next one. The important aspect is how we live this life. What we learn, how we cope with everything. Because, if you try and see it that we, in the end, what we learn throughout our entire experience with the world and with the unknown is what we will take with us in order to use and to survive in the next world. Coping with the new experience is in fact coping with the new us.

“The association of meaning with that which is unattainable and beyond experience introduces an untenable opposition between life and death.”⁶ Nevertheless, just picturing how the current life will be in the next one or how the current you will transform or maybe just the same means nothing if it ends up taking over you. Every new experience is different but we cannot let it take over. It is called an experience for a reason. I, for one, do believe that the reason is to show us that no matter how hard a new experience is, it is not the end...it is just something that we are meant to learn from, embrace it as a whole, analyze it, visualize it but keep moving forward with what we know as our life.

“Who can ignore today that we are part of the evolution of all species, of the universal flow of life; that the formation of the sun and the earth extends our lineage even further back in time, right down to matter, to the oxygen breathed by the first living creatures, to the atoms that compose us and which once were part of long-dead stars—that the universe had a beginning?”⁷ In order to be able to cope with something you need to start somewhere. As I have mentioned before, starting with the first breath that we take we form our own world, our own starting point if you may call it that way. It might seem as something usual or something that does not carry such an important aspect to it. But in fact it is the exact fundament of everything that we know. If you put that into perspective and try to apply the same thinking to everything that one experiences you will find quite a repetitive pattern. You should find life – because after all, life is formed of repetitive patterns.

It is why we can apply what we learn from a new experience to the next one and so on. They all share a pattern just like we do. But what separates one from another is how each uses that pattern. So what we have learnt from a previous one can be used

³ Ibidem, p.445

⁴ Ibidem, p.239

⁵ Hans-Georg Gadamer, *The Beginning of Knowledge*, Continuum, New York, 2002, p.64

⁶ Nicholas Davey, *Unquiet Understanding. Gadamer's Philosophical Hermeneutics*, State University of New York Press, Albany, 2006, p.138

⁷ Roland Omnès, *Quantum Philosophy. Understanding and Interpreting Contemporary Science*, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 1999, p.81

Coping With the New Experience

in the current one in order to find something new and use that in the next. This might not seem as much but in reality this is everything. If we do not try and learn something from every experience that we face and make one more step in that direction, put into use what we have learned, we will eventually get stuck repeating the same pattern but in different forms.

CONCLUSIONS

COPING with the new experience does not apply only to us, living beings. On the contrary. It is a term extended to everything including the Universe that we know and if we can extend that even further we can easily say that it applies to everything that exists even though not everything has been discovered. Being faced with the same pattern but in different forms gives us the real opportunity to show our work and to prove to us that we are indeed worth it. It is said that everything is a lesson...I believe that what is important here is to learn how to embrace it and to learn how to never stop learning.

Going through life, discovering everything that we can in this world, learning all that we are able to learn, challenging us to get out of the world that is our safe place and set foot into the world which is the unknown one is the first encounter we have with what we know as coping with a new experience. What is left is simply to start living. To ask all the questions even though they may seem wrong. To try everything even though we are afraid. To let our minds run free. The Universe as we know it is indeed a repetitive pattern but at the same time is a new experience in every moment because we are in it...we are the ones who get to make the choices and put into actions what we discover.

When we will start to ask ourselves what coping with a new experience means to each one...I believe that will be the moment in which we will start and understand what exactly we are all doing here. But until then, well until then we need to experience what this unknown world has to offer and maybe step out of our inside world and step into this one just a little bit more.

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